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Influence of School Plant on Students' Academic Performance in Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the influence of school plant on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. Four research questions and hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The analytical survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of this study was Senior Secondary School students in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State which is 47,297. The sample size of the study was 400 students arrived at using Taro Yamane's Formula. The instrument for data collection was a researchers'-developed questionnaire titled the School Plant and Student Academic Performance Questionnaire (SPSAPQ). In order to ascertain the reliability of the instrument, a reliability test was conducted on 30 students within the area of study that are not part of the sample for the main study. Data was collated and analysed for reliability using Cronbach Alpha correlation co-efficient. A reliability coefficient of 0.86 was realized for the instrument. The questionnaire was made up of 20 items and followed the Likert modified four-point scale in which respondents indicated their levels of agreement with the statements made by ticking any of the four options of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). The options had numerical values of 4, 3, 2 and 1 points respectively. The data were analysed based on the research questions using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation and the hypotheses were tested using the Chi-square (X^2) goodness of fit test at .05 level of significance, with 2.50 serving as the criterion mean for decision making on the items to be responded to and below 2.50 was considered negative and disagree. The findings of the study were as follows; classroom has significant influence on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State; library has significant influence on students' academic performance in secondary schools; laboratory has significant influence on students' academic performance in secondary schools and playground has significant influence on students' academic performance in secondary schools. Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made among others; given the significant influence of classrooms on students' academic performance, it is imperative for educational institutions to prioritize the optimization of classroom environments and it is crucial for educational institutions to prioritize the development and maintenance of well-equipped and accessible library spaces.

Keywords: School Classrooms, Library, Laboratory, Playground and Academic Performance.

INTRODUCTION

Schools are institutions set up for the purpose of shaping students into desirable individuals of the society. They transmit into the students the values of the society and prepare them for the task of national development. Everything that goes on in the school environment is summarized as teaching and learning. Therefore, when students are enrolled into schools, this is done with the hope that they adjust academically, socially and psychologically so that they can perform to their highest potentials. The success of the teaching-learning process is ascertained through the academic performance of students deduced from series of activities including assessments, exams, extracurricular activities or recreational activities among others. The outcome of what is planned and taught to learners is measured through their academic performance, which is an important parameter in measuring success of students (Wuave, 2023). The concept of academic performance is inevitable in any formal educational institution. It expresses the learning achievement of an individual or a group at the end of an academic programme. It is a criterion for ascertaining the capabilities of a student from which his potentials could be assimilated, retained, recalled and communicated based on his knowledge of what has been learnt (Joe, Kpolovie, Osonwa & Iderima, 2014). The learning environment which can be said to be the school plant is an important factor in learning. A friendly and an inspiring school plant is capable of increasing academic performance of students (Azever, Gire, Kpernyam & Akpe, 2019).

School plant often refers to the physical infrastructure or facilities of a school. This includes buildings, classrooms, laboratories, libraries, playgrounds, and other physical structures that make up the school environment. Maintaining and developing a school plant is crucial for providing a conducive learning atmosphere (Azever *et al.*, 2019). School plant is the controlled environments which facilitates teaching and learning process as well as protect the wellbeing of the occupants. The main objective of a school plant is to satisfy educational goals which have been predetermined by educational planners. A school plant enhances better school programmes and the community needs by providing a place for psychological and physical safety for students and teachers. It also enhances the academic performance of students (Onuorah & Nwankwo, 2022). Various aspects of the school plant have been found to influence the academic performance of students. In the current study, the researcher aims to find out how school plant facilities like classroom, library, laboratory and playground can influence the academic performance of students.

School classrooms are physical structures, roofed with zinc and ceiling, which protect teachers and students from rain, sun, heat, and cold (Nwagwu, 2010). Nwagwu further posits that school classrooms represent a school learning environment that has a tremendous influence on the comfort, safety, and performance of teachers. They are also a place where virtually all academic and administrative activities are carried out. Similarly, Fenker (2014) maintains that school classrooms support the operations of a school. Moreover, for teachers' job performance to be enhanced, and for effective teaching and learning to take place in any educational setting, there must be provision for adequate and quality school classrooms. Such provision of classrooms as a necessity in the school setting could also bring about the need to provide a school library stocked with books for students to not only read but also conduct research.

A school library is an extension of classroom activities with the purpose of making education more effective (Ekpo & Bassey, 2011). The Federal Republic of Nigeria, in its National Policy on Education (2013), recommended the provision of functional school libraries stocked with appropriate media resources meant to promote sound and effective teaching and learning activities, boost students' reading habits, and motivate students to achieve desired academic outcomes. The minimum standard for school libraries according to the policy, should consist of books, pamphlets, paper cuttings, gazettes and government publications, atlases, maps, and charts, photography records, films, record players, cassette tapes/players, film projections, slides, pictures, photographs, and periodicals. A well-designed and well-equipped library can have a positive impact on students' academic performance in several ways. Libraries contribute to the development of students' information literacy skills. They learn to locate, evaluate, and use information effectively, which is essential for academic success. Libraries, as integral components of educational institutions, contribute significantly to creating a conducive learning environment. When

well-utilized, they can positively impact students' academic performance by providing resources, fostering skills development, and offering spaces for focused study and collaboration. The researcher observes that the unavailability of a school library may demoralize teachers and make them incapable of efficiently performing their assigned jobs. Moreover, schools that have libraries without laboratories for science students to carry out experiments may affect their performances, as well as teachers' ability to measure their progress in teaching the students. This calls for the need for school laboratories.

A school laboratory is a building specially designed for teaching and learning by demonstrating theoretical phenomena in practical terms (Yara & Otieno, 2010). The authors further posit that a school laboratory is very essential for the teaching of sciences, and the success of any science course is much dependent on the laboratory provisions made for it. Effective teaching and learning can only take place in a school that has a well-equipped and maintained laboratory. According to Morohunfola (2015), school laboratory is an inseparable part of teaching and learning in both secondary and tertiary institutions and should be properly planned to serve the purpose of its existence in the school. The contribution of the school laboratory is enormous if the laboratory is properly planned, maintained and managed; it encourages students' interest in learning of science while it helps the science teachers in teaching, carrying out experiment, research and professional development (Onuorah & Nwankwo, 2022). Laboratories play a crucial role in enhancing the academic performance of secondary school students, particularly in subjects like science and technology. Laboratories provide students with hands-on, practical experiences that reinforce theoretical concepts taught in the classroom. This hands-on learning approach helps solidify understanding and retention of subject matter. Engaging in experiments encourages students to think critically, analyze data, and draw conclusions. This fosters problem-solving skills and a deeper understanding of scientific principles. According to Hofstein and Lunetta (2014), the school laboratory offers opportunities for productive, cooperative interaction among students and has the potential to promote a positive environment, which invariably influences students' academic performance. This goes beyond just the provision of a school laboratory; hence, teachers sometimes get exhausted after work and may seek a place to relieve their stress. Such situations may call for the need for a school playground for both teachers and students, hence the saying that 'all work and no play makes Jack a dull boy.

A playground is another school plant that seems to influence students' academic performance, as speculated by education stakeholders. A playground is a place with a specific design for students to play, and it may either be indoors or outdoors (Ediho, 2019). Ediho further identifies playground facilities, including all recreational equipment such as seesaws, merry-go-rounds, swing sets, slides, jungle gyms, chin-up bars, sandboxes, spring riders, monkey bars, overhead ladders, trapeze rings, playhouses, play fields, and mazes. Many of these playground facilities also include facilities for playing informal games or adult sports, such as a basketball court, which helps students develop physical coordination, strength, and flexibility. While the primary purpose of a playground is recreational and physical development, it can indirectly influence academic performance in several ways. Regular physical activity on the playground promotes overall health and well-being. Students who are physically active tend to have better concentration, improved mood, and enhanced cognitive function—all of which contribute to better academic performance. Breaks for physical activity, including time on the playground, have been linked to increased attention and concentration in the classroom. Students who have the opportunity to move and play during breaks are often more focused when they return to academic tasks.

Effective and efficient students' academic performance in secondary schools anywhere may not thrive well under poor environmental conditions. In the same vein, Abenga (2016) opines that improved environmental conditions lead to higher intelligence scores, reduce the stress of teaching and administrative tasks, while poor environmental conditions reduce these scores, create more tension, and result in better teachers' job inefficiency. The area of study also seems not to be an exception to such a situation. It is against this background that the researcher sees it necessary to investigate the influence of environmental conditions on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Rivers State, with a particular focus on school buildings, libraries, laboratories, and playgrounds.

Statement of the Problem

School plant is the physical environment in which teaching and learning take place. It includes the school site, buildings, classrooms, furniture, equipment, and other facilities. The school plant plays an important role in student academic performance, as it can provide a supportive and conducive learning environment, or it can hinder learning. In Port Harcourt metropolis of Rivers State, Nigeria, many secondary schools have inadequate school plant facilities. This includes classrooms that are overcrowded and poorly ventilated, laboratories that are lacking in essential equipment, and libraries that are insufficiently stocked with books and other resources. In addition, many schools lack basic amenities such as clean water and sanitation facilities. The poor state of the school plant in Port Harcourt metropolis has a negative impact on student academic performance. Students who learn in overcrowded and poorly ventilated classrooms are more likely to experience fatigue and difficulty concentrating. Students who do not have access to well-equipped laboratories and libraries are limited in their ability to learn science and other subjects effectively. And students who lack access to clean water and sanitation facilities are more likely to get sick, which can also disrupt their learning. The influence of school plant on student academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State is a serious problem that needs to be addressed. By improving the school plant infrastructure and providing students with the facilities they need to learn, the government and other stakeholders can help to improve student academic performance and outcomes.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to investigate the influence of school plant on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Ascertain the influence of classroom on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.
2. Determine the influence of library on students' academic performance in secondary schools.
3. Assess the influence of laboratory on students' academic performance in secondary schools.
4. Ascertain the influence of playground on students' academic performance in secondary schools.

Research Question

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the influence of classroom on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State?
2. What is the influence of library on students' academic performance in secondary schools?
3. What is the influence of laboratory on students' academic performance in secondary schools?
4. What is the influence of playground on students' academic performance in secondary schools?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. Classroom has no significant influence on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.
2. Library has no significant influence on students' academic performance in secondary schools.
3. Laboratory has no significant influence on students' academic performance in secondary schools.
4. Playground has no significant influence on students' academic performance in secondary schools.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The analytical survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of this study was 47, 297 Senior Secondary School students in 37 public schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. The sample size of the study was 400 students sampled using Taro Yamane's formula. The instrument for data collection was a researcher-developed questionnaire titled the School Plant and Student Academic Performance Questionnaire (SPSAPQ). The questionnaire was made up of 20 items and followed the Likert modified four-point scale in which respondents indicated their levels of agreement with the statements made by ticking any of the four options of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and

Strongly Disagree (SD). The options had numerical values of 4, 3, 2 and 1 points respectively. In order to ascertain the reliability of the instrument, a reliability test was conducted on 30 students within the area of study that are not part of the sample for the main study. Data was collated and analysed for reliability using Cronbach Alpha correlation co-efficient. A reliability coefficient of 0.86 was realized for the instrument. The data were analysed based on the research questions using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation and the hypotheses were tested using the Chi-square (X^2) goodness of fit test at .05 level of significance, with 2.50 serving as the criterion mean for decision making on the items to be responded to and below 2.50 was considered negative and disagree.

Analysis of Research Questions

Research Question 1: *What is the influence of classroom on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State?*

Table 1: Analysis of Influence of Classroom on Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1	We have enough classrooms for learning.	100	180	64	56	2.81	.968	Accepted
2	Our classrooms are of good size.	200	144	24	32	3.28	.896	Accepted
3	The buildings are well located for quick accessibility.	156	180	44	20	3.18	.818	Accepted
4	Our classrooms are well ventilated.	112	204	52	32	2.99	.855	Accepted
5	The buildings are of good conditions.	120	160	80	40	2.90	.945	Accepted
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation $\bar{X}= 3.032$ SD= .8964								Accepted

Table 1 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 1 to 5 are 2.81, 3.28, 3.18, 2.99, and 2.90 with corresponding standard deviations of .968, .896, .818, .855, and .945 respectively. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 3.032 with the cluster standard deviation of .8964 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that classroom has influence on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Research Question 2: *What is the influence of library on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State?*

Table 2: Analysis of Influence of Library on Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
6	The library is accommodated in a good building.	320	60	20	0	3.75	.537	Accepted
7	The library is well stocked with current and relevant textbooks.	160	180	40	20	3.20	.813	Accepted
8	The library is always supplied with current newspaper and magazine.	128	120	80	72	2.76	1.089	Accepted
9	Library facilities help students to study effectively leading to academic performance.	120	240	32	8	3.18	.655	Accepted
10	We have competent library staff to guide us on the correct usage of the library facilities.	140	164	56	40	3.01	.945	Accepted
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation $\bar{X}= 3.18$ SD= .8078								Accepted

Table 2 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 6 to 10 are 3.75, 3.20, 2.76, 3.18, and 3.01 with corresponding standard deviations of .537, .813, 1.089, .655, and .945 respectively. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 3.18 with the cluster standard deviation of .8078 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that library has influence on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Research Question 3: *What is the influence of laboratory on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State?*

Table 3: Analysis of Influence of Laboratory on Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
11	A well-planned science laboratory stocked with relevant chemicals and equipment will influence teaching and learning of science.	172	168	0	60	3.13	1.008	Accepted
12	Poorly planned, unventilated, and dilapidated laboratory facilities will have influence on teaching and learning of science subjects.	88	246	6	60	2.91	.910	Accepted
13	Damage caused to laboratory facilities will have influence on teaching and learning of science subjects.	176	146	18	60	3.10	1.039	Accepted
14	Absence of science laboratory in schools will have influence on teaching and learning of science subjects.	82	234	24	60	2.85	.918	Accepted
15	Regular repair of laboratory and provision of chemicals and equipment improves students' academic performance.	186	136	0	78	3.08	1.115	Accepted
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation $\bar{X}= 3.014$ SD= .998								Accepted

Table 3 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 11 to 15 are 3.13, 2.91, 3.10, 2.85, and 3.08 with corresponding standard deviations of 1.008, .910, 1.039, .918, and 1.115 respectively. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 3.438 with the cluster standard deviation of .5804 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that laboratory has influence on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Research Question 4

What is the influence of playground on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State?

Table 4:

Analysis of Influence of Playground on Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

S/N	Item description	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
16	I am happy with the different playgrounds drawn in the school yard.	120	160	80	40	2.90	.945	Accepted
17	The figures such as triangle, pentagon, hexagon, circle and rectangle in the school yard help you learn.	320	60	20	0	3.75	.537	Accepted
18	The success I get in the games we play increase my self-confidence.	160	180	40	20	3.20	.813	Accepted
19	The space for playground in my school is spacious enough for different activities.	183	139	42	36	3.17	.946	Accepted
20	I feel refreshed after recreational activities on the playground.	170	172	1	57	3.14	.990	Accepted
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation $\bar{X}= 3.232$ SD= .8462								Accepted

Table 4 indicates that the mean ratings of respondents' responses for items 16 to 20 are 2.90, 3.75, 3.20, 3.17, and 3.14 with corresponding standard deviations of .945, .537, .813, .946, and .990 respectively. Respondents rated all items above the 2.50 cut-off point. The cluster mean of 3.232 with the cluster standard deviation of .8462 is above the cut-off point of 2.50 which indicates that playground has

influence on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Hypotheses Testing

In testing the hypotheses of this study, Chi-square (X^2) was used to test the responses of respondents at .05 level of significance.

Hypothesis 1

Classroom has no significant influence on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Table 5: Chi-square Test of Influence of Classroom on Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X^2_{cal}	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	96.320	.000	Sig.
SA	100	100.0					
A	180	100.0					
D	64	100.0					
SD	56	100.0					
Total	400						

Table 5 revealed that $\chi^2 = 96.320$, $df=3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degree of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that classroom has no significant influence on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State is therefore rejected. This implies that classroom has significant influence on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Hypothesis 2

Library has no significant influence on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Table 6: Chi-square Test of Influence of Library on Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X^2_{cal}	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	200.00	.000	Sig.
SA	160	100.0					
A	180	100.0					
D	40	100.0					
SD	20	100.0					
Total	400						

Table 6 revealed that $\chi^2 = 200.00$, $df=3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degree of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that library has no significant influence on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State is therefore rejected. This implies that library has significant influence on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Hypothesis 3

Laboratory has no significant influence on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Table 7: Chi-square Test of Influence of Laboratory on Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X^2_{cal}	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	256.560	.000	Sig.
SA	82	100.0					
A	234	100.0					
D	24	100.0					
SD	60	100.0					
Total	400						

Table 7 revealed that $\chi^2 = 256.560$, $df = 3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degree of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that laboratory has no significant influence on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State is therefore rejected. This implies that laboratory has significant influence on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Hypothesis 4

Playground has no significant influence on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Table 8: Chi-square Test of Influence of Laboratory on Academic Performance of Secondary School Students in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

Response	O	E	df.	Level of sign.	X ² cal	P-value	Decision
			3	.05	158.700	.000	Sig.
SA	183	100.0					
A	139	100.0					
D	42	100.0					
SD	36	100.0					
Total	400						

Table 8 revealed that $\chi^2 = 158.700$, $df = 3$ and $p = 0.00$. Since the p-value of 0.00 is less than the set alpha-value of 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) at 3 degree of freedom, the null hypothesis which states that playground has no significant influence on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State is therefore rejected. This implies that playground has significant influence on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The discussion of the findings of this research is organized around the research questions and hypotheses for ease of reading and comprehension. The four null hypotheses that were postulated and tested were all rejected.

The first finding of the study revealed that classroom has significant influence on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. Classrooms serve as the physical and social context where students engage with curriculum, interact with peers, and receive instruction from teachers. This finding is similar to those Elujekwute, Daagu and Ikwen (2021) and Asiegbu and Amojó (2021) who found that factors such as classroom layout, seating arrangement, lighting, temperature, and resources available can all influence students' concentration, motivation, and overall learning experience. Additionally, the classroom atmosphere, including teacher-student relationships and peer dynamics, plays a crucial role in creating a supportive and conducive learning environment.

The second finding of the study library has significant influence on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. The revelation that libraries wield substantial influence on students' academic performance in secondary schools underscores the pivotal role of these spaces in fostering learning outcomes. This finding is similar to that of Atolagbe (2019) who found that school plant has a role to play on the effectiveness of instruction and the ultimate performance of students in their examinations. Suleiman, Hanafi and Tanslikhan (2018) also found that access to a well-equipped library offers students opportunities for independent study, research, and critical thinking development thereby influencing their academic performance positively. Moreover, libraries often provide resources beyond textbooks, including digital materials, reference sources, and educational technology, which can enrich students' learning experiences. Additionally, libraries offer a conducive environment for quiet study and collaboration, supporting diverse learning styles.

The third finding of the study revealed that laboratory has significant influence on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. The discovery that laboratories exert a significant influence on students' academic performance in secondary schools

underscores the vital role of hands-on experiential learning in education. Laboratories provide a unique environment where students can engage directly with scientific concepts, theories, and methodologies. This finding is similar to that of Onuorah and Nwankwo (2022), the researchers observed that through practical experimentation, observation, and analysis, students deepen their understanding of scientific principles and develop essential skills such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and data interpretation. Furthermore, laboratory activities often stimulate curiosity, creativity, and a passion for inquiry-driven learning among students. Access to well-equipped laboratories not only enhances students' academic achievement but also fosters a deeper appreciation for the sciences and prepares them for future academic and professional pursuits in STEM fields. Therefore, investing in and prioritizing laboratory resources within secondary schools is crucial for cultivating a scientifically literate and academically successful student body.

The fourth finding of the study revealed that playground has significant influence on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. While traditionally viewed as spaces for recreation and socialization, playgrounds offer invaluable opportunities for students to engage in physical exercise, which has been consistently linked to improved academic outcomes. This finding is similar to that of Azever *et al.*, (2019) who found in a study that that recreational facilities have significant influence on students' academic performance. Atolagbe (2019) also observed that playground had significant influence on academic performance of students. The author opined that regular physical activity has been shown to enhance cognitive function, including attention, memory, and problem-solving skills, all of which are essential for academic success. Additionally, playgrounds provide a break from the academic routine, allowing students to release energy, reduce stress, and rejuvenate their focus for subsequent learning activities.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that school plant has significant influence on students' academic performance in secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis of Rivers State. Based on the findings the following recommendations were made;

1. Given the significant influence of classrooms on students' academic performance, it is imperative for educational institutions to prioritize the optimization of classroom environments. This can be achieved through careful attention to factors such as classroom layout, lighting, temperature control, and the availability of resources.
2. It is crucial for educational institutions to prioritize the development and maintenance of well-equipped and accessible library spaces. Schools should invest in expanding their library collections to encompass a diverse range of resources, including books, digital materials, and educational technology. Moreover, promoting a culture of reading and research through library programs and initiatives can foster a lifelong love for learning among students.
3. Educational institutions should prioritize the development and utilization of well-equipped and innovative laboratory facilities. Schools should invest in modernizing laboratory equipment and materials to ensure students have access to hands-on experiential learning opportunities. Additionally, fostering a culture of inquiry-based learning and scientific exploration within the laboratory environment can enhance students' critical thinking, problem-solving, and analytical skills.
4. Schools should prioritize the design and maintenance of safe and engaging playground spaces that encourage movement, exploration, and social interaction. Incorporating regular outdoor recess breaks into the school day can provide students with opportunities to release energy, reduce stress, and enhance focus for subsequent academic activities.

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